

FATIGUE LIFE PREDICTION OF EPOXY COATING ON COMPOSITES SUBJECTED TO WATERDROP IMPACT

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ABSTRACT

Wind energy is one of the prominent renewable sources of electricity. The erosion of the leading edge of the wind turbine blade due to raindrops, sand and other particles is of the utmost concern owing to the high tip velocities associated with the increasing blade span. The deteriorated leading edge of the blade reduces its aerodynamic efficiency and the power output. Gel-coats and polyurethane coating/paint systems are used to improve the erosion resistance of the turbine blades. This paper presents a finite element model to study the water drop impact on glass fibre reinforced composite coated with epoxy gel-coat. The rainfall data of Mumbai region in India is obtained for three consecutive years 2015, 2016 and 2017. The fatigue life of the coating is predicted against the obtained rainfall data.

1 INTRODUCTION

Wind turbine installation is growing at an exponential rate across the globe. India has a gross wind power potential of 302 GW with the world's fourth largest installed wind capacity of 34.98 GW, as of October 2018 [1]. The country is heading towards an installation of a total 60 GW capacity by 2022 along with an offshore installation of 5 GW by 2022 and 30 GW by 2030 [1]. An increase in the blade span of the turbine is known to increase the power output [2]. Fig.1 shows the blade tip velocities can go as high as 120 m/s. The operating conditions of the turbine subjects the leading edge to raindrop, sand, hail, ice and other particle impact. Moreover, pre-erosion by liquid impact can further accelerate the erosion by solid particles [4]. The leading edge erosion could increase the drag by 6 % to 500 % depending on the amount of erosion [3]. Further, the lift coefficient is also predicted to drop by 0.17 along with an annual energy production loss as high as 25%.

Figure 1: Blade tip velocities vs rotor diameter [7].

Composite materials which use thermosetting epoxy or polyester matrix reinforced with carbon or glass fibre are general choice of materials for the turbine blades owing to their high specific strength

and stiffness properties. The erosion is referred as a systems' property [5]. Implying, the wear to be determined by the operational conditions, the physics of interaction and the material properties of the blade and the solid particles and/or droplets. Epoxy or polyester gel-coats and/or polyurethane coating/paints are used to improve the erosion resistance of the leading edge turbine blades [8].

Various experimental methods like whirling arm, single droplet impact, multiple impact waterjets and rocket sled tests used to predict the fatigue life of the coatings/paints have limitations in the aspects of costs, droplet size variation, and reproducibility and may incorporate unrealistic forces and boundary conditions. In that case, an analytical model to predict the fatigue life of the coating might come in handy. Slot et al. [6] has developed an analytical model on the life of coating materials. While a finite element model has also been used to simulate the droplet erosion phenomenon [8]. However, none of the studies conducted so far have been able to predict an expected fatigue life of a coating against the rainfall data of the location.

This paper presents a finite element model of water drop impact using explicit dynamics tool. The material under consideration is glass fibre reinforced composite coated with epoxy gel-coat. The rainfall data of three consecutive years 2015, 2016 and 2017 is obtained from the Regional Meteorological Department, Santacruz, Mumbai. The damage accumulation is calculated using the Palmgren-Miner's damage accumulation rule. Further, the fatigue life of the coating is calculated against the rainfall data.

2 MODELLING

Finite element modelling is done using the explicit dynamics tool in ANSYS. The composite material is modelled as a 10x10 mm rectangular plate with a 2 mm thickness. The coating has a thickness of 0.6 mm. The material used for composite is a unidirectional S-glass/epoxy composite, which uses a linear orthotropic model. The coating material uses a linear isotropic model for epoxy resin. The rain/water drop is modelled as a sphere with a diameter of 3 mm. The raindrop material used is 'WATER', which uses a shock equation of state. The raindrop is modelled to impact the centre of the plate with a velocity of 140 m/s. The displacement of the base of the plate along the direction of drop velocity is constrained. Table 1 shows the boundary conditions of the impact.

Direction	X	Y	Z
Displacement of the base of the plate	Free	Free	0 (ramped)
Velocity of the droplet	0	0	-140 m/s

Table 1: Boundary conditions of the impact.

The coated composite is modelled in the lagrangian scheme with hexahedral mesh biased towards the centre. A tetrahedral mesh with the element size of 0.06 mm is used to define the volume of the droplet in the eulerian domain with a total cell count of 7×10^5 . Table 2 shows the mesh characteristics of the plate. The interaction between the composite and the coat is set as bonded and that between the coat and the water drop is set to be frictionless. The time period of simulation was set to 10 μ s with a time-step of 0.01 μ s.

Along the cross-section	
Edge sizing type	Biased
Biased type	-----
Growth factor	1.05
No of divisions	100
Total edges	16
Along the thickness	
Edge sizing type	Uniform
Total edges	8
Number of divisions (coat)	12
Number of divisions (Composite)	40

Table 2: Mesh characteristics of the plate.

3 MATERIAL PROPERTIES

3.1 MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

The mechanical properties of the water droplet, S-glass/epoxy composite and the epoxy coating are shown in table 3.

Density, ρ	998 kg/m ³
Equation of state	Linear Shock EOS
Grunesian coefficient, Γ	0
Velocity of sound, C	1647 m/s
S ₁	1.921
S ₂	0

Table 3.1: Mechanical properties of water.

Density, ρ	2000 kg/m ³
Young's modulus X direction, E _x	50000 MPa
Young's modulus Y direction, E _y	8000 MPa
Young's modulus Z direction, E _z	8000 MPa
Poisson's ratio X direction, μ_{xy}	0.3
Poisson's ratio Y direction, μ_{yz}	0.4
Poisson's ratio Z direction, μ_{xz}	0.3
Shear modulus X direction, G _{xy}	5000 MPa
Shear modulus Y direction, G _{yz}	3846.2 MPa
Shear modulus Z direction, G _{xz}	5000 MPa
Ultimate tensile strength, σ_{uts}	700 MPa

Table 3.2: Mechanical properties of S-glass/epoxy composite.

Density, ρ	1160 kg/m ³
Young's modulus, E	3780 MPa
Poisson's ratio, μ	0.35
Bulk modulus, K	4200 MPa
Shear modulus, G	1400 MPa
Ultimate tensile strength, σ_{uts}	200 MPa

Table 3.3: Mechanical properties of epoxy resin.

3.2 S-N curve

The fatigue parameters for the epoxy matrix are obtained by retrieving the data from the S-N curve characteristics presented in [9]. Fig. 2 shows the plot of the retrieved S-N curve data. The Wohler equation below gives the relation between the fatigue parameters.

$$N = \sigma_{uts} S^{-b} \quad (1)$$

Where N is number of cycles, σ_{uts} is the ultimate tensile strength of the material, S is load amplitude and b is slope parameter.

Figure 2: S-N curve for the epoxy matrix [9].

4 STRESS VS TIME HISTORY

The finite element analysis gives the stress vs time history of the plate. The stress vs time history depicts a random but continuous loading on the plate with the maximum Equivalent (von-Mises) stress of 152.12 MPa at 1.0402 μ s. This poses difficulties in expressing the time history into equivalent number of counting cycles, incremental fatigue damage due to each cycle and applying a suitable damage accumulation rule to calculate total fatigue damage. Fig. 3 depicts the Equivalent (von-Mises) stress vs time history. A rainflow cycle counting method developed by Rychlik [11] is coded in MATLAB to convert the stress vs time history into equivalent number of counting cycles with corresponding values of stress amplitude and mean stress. The rainflow matrix obtained is shown in fig. 4.

Figure 3: Stress vs time history.

Figure 4: Rainflow matrix of epoxy coating.

Mean stress ratio obtained from the rainflow matrix is not zero. Pavlov's mean stress correction expression in Eq. (2) is used to obtain equivalent stress amplitude at zero mean stress ratio.

$$Seq = \frac{Sa}{1 - \frac{Sm}{\sigma_{uts}}} \quad (2)$$

Where Seq is the equivalent stress amplitude, Sa is the stress amplitude, Sm is the mean stress and σ_{uts} is the ultimate strength of the material.

5 RAINFALL DATA

An hourly rainfall data for Mumbai at Santacruz (SCZ) and Colaba (COL) stations for three consecutive years 2015, 2016 and 2017 is obtained from the Regional Meteorological Department Santacruz, Mumbai. The statistical variation of mean drop diameter with different rain intensities is represented in table 4. It can be observed that the mean drop diameters increase with the rainfall intensity. This is due to the fact that small raindrop coalesce to form a big drop. This can also be verified by observing the probability density function of drop size for different rain intensities in fig. 5. With the increasing rain intensity, the mean drop diameter in the range of 1-2 mm is maximum followed by 2-4 mm. While that above 4 mm diameter are significantly low. A uniform mean drop diameter of 3 mm is therefore assumed for the obtained rainfall intensity data.

Diameter (mm)						
Rainfall rate (mm/hour)	0-1	1-2	2-3	3-4	4-5	>5
0-2	43.6	5.54	0.17	0.01	0	0
2-4	220.74	64.74	7.10	0.71	0.05	0
4-6	268.25	125.72	7.03	0.88	0.15	0
6-8	202.62	152.54	22.61	0.85	0.07	0
8-10	220	197.8	30.4	1.2	0	0
10-20	239.88	216.36	45.76	6.84	0.92	0.12
20-40	119.41	132.91	56.59	12.39	0.95	18.65
40-60	270.13	511.	207.97	37.77	2.64	1.90
>60	239.41	495.59	223.06	37.76	1.47	39.53

Table 4: Rainfall intensity vs droplet diameter [10].

Figure 5: Probability density function of raindrop size [7].

The self-recording rain gauge has a measuring cylinder of diameter 100 mm with a rotating drum mounted above the measuring cylinder. While the area of the rectangular specimen is 100 mm². The rain intensity data thus obtained is accounted for by the factor of area ratio of the rain gauge and the plate given in Eq. (3)

$$\frac{Ac}{Ap} = 78.57 \quad (3)$$

Where Ac is the area of the measuring cylinder and Ap is the area of the plate. Table 5 displays the rainfall duration at each station, every year along with the number of droplets impacting on the plate and the time interval between two consecutive raindrops. The average time interval between two consecutive raindrops is 9.52 s. This time interval is too high for two consecutive impacts to interfere. Hence, only single impact damage is taken into account for the fatigue life prediction.

Year	Station	Drops/hour (rain gauge)	Drops/ hour (10x10 plate)	Drops/year (10x10plate)	Time interval (s)	Duration of rainfall (hours)
2015	SCZ	24223	308	13112	11.68831169	606
2015	COL	26390	335	11851	10.74626866	611
2016	SCZ	27779	353	16779	10.19830028	955
2016	COL	27779	353	14302	10.19830028	851
2017	SCZ	50002	636	17255	5.660377358	772
2017	COL	32779	417	13625	8.633093525	695

Table 5: Rainfall intensity data.

6 FATIGUE LIFE PREDICTION

6.1 DAMAGE ACCUMULATION RULE

Palmgren-Miner's damage accumulation rule is applied to calculate the cumulative damage due to each load cycle. Substituting equation (2) in (1), the number of cycles required for failure against each value of equivalent load amplitude is calculated as given below:

$$N = \sigma_{us} S e q^{-b} \quad (4)$$

Further, the damage accumulation due to each load cycle will be $1/N_i$. The fractional damage due to n_i such cycles will be n_i/N_i . The material is considered to fail when damage the cumulative damage equals to 1. The cumulative damage accumulation is given by

$$D = \sum_1^k \frac{n_i}{N_i} \quad (5)$$

6.2 IMPACT LOCATIONS

The plate is discretized into 16 grid points and the impacts are assumed to occur on these points, as shown in fig. 6. The total number of droplets impacting each location at each station is obtained randomly using a MATLAB code.

Figure 6: Discretization of the plate.

7 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The cumulative single impact damage calculated using Palmgren-Miner's rule is 0.000961987. The average number of droplets impacting the plate every year at both the stations is 14487. This gives the epoxy coating an average fatigue life of about 26 days. It further implies that the coat is damaged completely by approximately 1040 impacts. However, this is the fatigue life of the coating assuming its exposure to continuous rainfall. However, the average rainfall duration per year is 750 hours. This gives the epoxy coating an average fatigue life of 306 days over a calendar year.

8 CONCLUSIONS

The leading edge erosion of the turbine blades and associated power loss is of a critical concern. This paper presents a numerical model of water drop impact on a composite plate to predict the fatigue life of an epoxy coating on the composite surface. Rainfall data of the Mumbai region in India was used to simulate the fatigue loading. The obtained results predict the fatigue life of the epoxy coating to be less than a calendar year. This value may further decrease with an increase in the rainfall intensity. The coating used for the analysis might be more suitable for low rainfall regions. Further studies need to be done to understand the effect of thickness of coating on the fatigue life.

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